

A high order accurate and provably stable fully discrete continuous Galerkin framework on summation-by-parts form for advection-diffusion equations

Mrityunjoy Mandal¹, Jan Nordström^{3,2*}, Arnaud G Malan¹

¹InCFD Research Group, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa.

^{2*}Department of Mathematics, Linköping University, Linköping, Sweden.

³Department of Mathematics and Applied Mathematics, University of Johannesburg, Johannesburg, South Africa.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): jan.nordstrom@liu.se;

Contributing authors: mrityunjoy.mandal@uct.ac.za;

arnaud.malan@uct.ac.za;

Abstract

We present a high-order accurate fully discrete numerical scheme for solving Initial Boundary Value Problems (IBVPs) within the Continuous Galerkin (CG)-based Finite Element framework. Both the spatial and time approximation in Summation-By-Parts (SBP) form are considered here. The initial and boundary conditions are imposed weakly using the Simultaneous Approximation Term (SAT) technique. The resulting SBP-SAT formulation yields an energy estimate in terms of the initial and external boundary data, leading to an energy-stable discretization in both space and time. The proposed method is evaluated numerically using the Method of Manufactured Solutions (MMS). The scheme achieves super-convergence in both spatial and temporal direction with accuracy $\mathcal{O}(p+2)$ for $p \geq 2$, where p refers to the degree of the Lagrange basis. In an application case, we show that the fully discrete formulation efficiently captures space-time variations even on coarse meshes, demonstrating the method's computational effectiveness.

Keywords: Initial boundary value problem, Time integration, Summation-by-parts, Weak initial and boundary conditions, Multistage, High order accuracy, Energy stability, Super-convergence

1 Introduction

In this work, we present a highly accurate, fully discrete, and energy-stable numerical scheme based on the SBP–SAT technique [1, 2]. The transient advection–diffusion equation is considered for various flow regimes, ranging from diffusion-dominated to advection-dominated cases. The SBP–SAT framework in the CG formulation was previously developed [3] for spatial discretizations, where a convergence rate of order $\mathcal{O}(p + 2)$ was observed when an explicit Runge–Kutta time integration scheme was employed with a sufficiently small time step. In the present work, we extend this framework to the temporal domain [4, 5]. For time discretization, both global and one-step multi-stage approaches are employed. The SAT technique is used to weakly impose both the initial and boundary conditions. The resulting formulation is provably stable and exhibits superconvergent behavior in both the temporal and spatial directions. To the best of our knowledge, such a highly accurate, fully discrete, and provably stable time integration scheme is not previously found within the CG framework.

For time integration of stiff IBVPs, implicit schemes are often preferred, as they relax the stability requirement on the time step size. Common examples of such methods include implicit Runge–Kutta schemes [6, 7], Backward Differentiation Formulas (BDF) [8, 9], and linear multistep methods [10, 11]. These approaches can be regarded as local methods since each time interval depends only on one or a few previous steps. In contrast, global methods consider the entire time domain, ranging from the initial time to the final time T . Previously developed global methods, such as spectral and collocation time approximations [12–14], are often considered impractical due to their high computational costs. Nevertheless, global methods exhibit unconditional stability and can achieve very high orders of accuracy. Moreover, they can be used to exactly mimic continuous energy estimates, a property that is rarely achieved by local methods. SBP in time [4] was introduced as a global method and was later [5] reformulated as a multistage method, retaining its global stability properties.

The paper is organized as follows. The continuous problem and the associated energy analysis are described in Section 2. The appropriate choice of boundary conditions and their weak imposition using SATs are also presented. The semi-discrete approximation of the continuous problem and its associated energy estimate are discussed in Section 3. Here, we also present the discrete energy approximation and prove stability in a manner similar to that of the continuous setting. The fully discrete scheme is discussed in detail, along with the energy analysis in Section 4. The one-step multistage technique is discussed in Section 5 and is also shown to be energy stable. Section 6 presents the numerical solutions for three different problems. First, we use the MMS to verify the order of temporal convergence of the formulation. Secondly, we evaluate the order of spatial convergence using another MMS, and lastly, we evaluate the performance of the combined effort by solving a wave propagation problem. Conclusions are presented in Section 7.

2 The continuous problem

Let us consider a one-dimensional domain $x \in \Omega = [x_0, x_1] = [0, 1]$ with the IBVP:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t u + a \partial_x u - \epsilon \partial_{xx} u &= 0, & 0 \leq x \leq 1, & t \geq 0, \\ au - \epsilon \partial_x u &= g_0(t), & x = 0, & t \geq 0, \\ \epsilon \partial_x u &= g_1(t), & x = 1, & t \geq 0, \\ u &= f(x), & 0 \leq x \leq 1, & t = 0. \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

In (2.1), $u = u(x, t)$ defines the solution field, and the constants $a > 0, \epsilon > 0$ denote the advection and diffusion coefficients, respectively. The partial differential operators ∂_t, ∂_x and ∂_{xx} define the temporal and spatial differentiations, respectively. The boundary operators are $(a - \epsilon \partial_x)$ and $\epsilon \partial_x$, the boundary data are g_0 and g_1 , while the initial data is represented by f .

2.1 Continuous energy analysis

By multiplying (2.1) with the solution and performing integration-by-parts in space, followed by the imposition of boundary conditions, we derive the following energy rate:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \|u\|^2 + 2\epsilon \|\partial_x u\|^2 = \frac{1}{a} \left[g_0^2 - (au - g_0)^2 \right] \Big|_{x=0} + \frac{1}{a} \left[g_1^2 - (au - g_1)^2 \right] \Big|_{x=1} \leq \frac{1}{a} (g_0^2 + g_1^2), \tag{2.2}$$

where $\|u\|^2 = \int_{\Omega} u^2 d\Omega$ and $\|\partial_x u\|^2 = \int_{\Omega} (\partial_x u)^2 d\Omega$. Time integration of (2.2) generates the energy estimate:

$$\|u(\cdot, T)\|^2 + 2\epsilon \int_0^T \|\partial_x u\|^2 dt = \|f\|^2 + \frac{1}{a} \int_0^T \left[(g_0^2 + g_1^2) - \left[(au - g_0)^2 + (au - g_1)^2 \right] \right] dt, \tag{2.3}$$

where the norm of the solution at final time and the time integration of the gradient of the solution are bounded by initial and boundary data. However, the strong imposition of boundary conditions may result in stability issues in the discrete setting [15]. In remedy, we will implement the boundary conditions in weak sense using penalty terms.

2.2 Weak imposition of boundary conditions for the continuous problem

Following [16], we impose the boundary conditions in (2.1) weakly by adding the SAT-like terms as:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t u + a \partial_x u - \epsilon \partial_{xx}^2 u &= \text{SAT} \text{ where } \text{SAT} = L_0 (\sigma_0 [(au - \epsilon \partial_x u) - g_0]) + L_1 (\sigma_1 [\epsilon \partial_x u - g_1]), \\ u(0) &= f. \end{aligned} \tag{2.4}$$

The lifting operators $L_i(\cdot)$ in the SAT term [17] are defined as $\int_{\Omega} \psi^T L_i(\phi) dx = \psi^T \phi|_{x=x_i}$ for smooth scalar functions ψ and ϕ . The penalty parameters σ_0 and σ_1 will be determined to ensure energy boundedness.

We again apply the energy method by multiplying (2.4) with the solution vector, integrating by parts, and taking $\sigma_0 = \sigma_1 = -1$ to obtain

$$\frac{d}{dt} \|u\|^2 + 2\epsilon \|\partial_x u\|^2 = \frac{1}{a} [g_0^2 - (au - g_0)^2]|_{x=0} + \frac{1}{a} [g_1^2 - (au - g_1)^2]|_{x=0} \leq \frac{1}{a} (g_0^2 + g_1^2), \quad (2.5)$$

which is identical to (2.2). Time integration of (2.5) leads to (2.3).

3 The semi-discrete approximation

For semi-discrete approximations in the CG framework, the computational domain Ω is discretized into N_{el} finite elements such that $\Omega = \cup \Omega^e$. The total number of global nodes becomes $(N + 1)$, representing the number of nodes in the spatial direction, where $N = (N_{\text{el}} \times p)$ and p refers to the degree of the Lagrange basis used. We begin by constructing the spatial operators in SBP form at the element level [18]. These element-level operators are then assembled to form the global operators. This construction will be applied also for the time discretization.

3.1 Constructions of the SBP operators at the element level for one-dimensional domain

For a single element, we employ the Lagrange basis (\mathcal{L}_i) to approximate the solution. As such, the trial function $u(x, t)$ is approximated by:

$$u^h(x, t) = \sum_{i=0}^p \mathcal{L}_i(x) U_i(t) = \mathcal{L}^T(x) \mathbf{U}(t), \quad (3.1)$$

where the total number of nodes per element is $(p + 1)$, and $\mathcal{L}(x)^T = [\mathcal{L}_0(x), \mathcal{L}_1(x), \dots, \mathcal{L}_p(x)]$ is the set of Lagrange polynomials of degree p . $\mathbf{U}(t) = [U_0(t), U_1(t), \dots, U_p(t)]$ denotes the set of time-dependent coefficients at node points.

We compute the element mass matrix (\mathbf{P}^e) and weak first order derivative operator (\mathbf{Q}_x^e) at the element level as (for details see [18]):

$$\mathbf{P}^e = \int_{\Omega^e} \mathcal{L} \mathcal{L}^T d\Omega^e \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{Q}_x^e = \int_{\Omega^e} \mathcal{L} (\partial_x \mathcal{L})^T d\Omega^e, \quad (3.2)$$

where $\int_{\Omega^e} (\cdot) d\Omega^e$ defines the integral over the element domain. The operator \mathbf{Q}_x^e is almost skew-symmetric since

$$\mathbf{Q}_x^e = \int_{\Omega^e} \mathcal{L} (\partial_x \mathcal{L})^T d\Omega^e = \mathcal{L} \mathcal{L}^T \Big|_0^p - \int_{\Omega^e} (\partial_x \mathcal{L}) \mathcal{L}^T d\Omega^e = \tilde{\mathbf{B}}^e - (\mathbf{Q}_x^e)^T, \quad (3.3)$$

where the boundary operator $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}^e = \text{diag}(-1, 0, \dots, 0, 1)$ contains non-zero values only on the boundary.

Similarly, we define the weak second-order derivative operator \mathbf{Q}_{xx}^e in SBP form at the element level as:

$$\mathbf{Q}_{xx}^e = \int_{\Omega^e} \mathcal{L} (\partial_{xx} \mathcal{L})^T d\Omega^e = \mathcal{L} (\partial_x \mathcal{L})^T \Big|_0^p - \int_{\Omega^e} (\partial_x \mathcal{L}) (\partial_x \mathcal{L})^T d\Omega^e. \quad (3.4)$$

Next, we map each element from the physical domain $x \in [0, l_x^e]$ (where l_x^e defines the length of the element) to the parametric domain $\xi \in [-1, 1]$ using the Jacobian $J = \partial x / \partial \xi = l_x^e / 2$ and compute the spatial integrals using Gauss-Lobatto (GL) quadrature. E.g., for a given function $f(x)$ the integral is computed as:

$$\int_{-1}^1 f(x) dx = \sum_{i=0}^p f(\xi_i) \omega_i |J|. \quad (3.5)$$

Here ξ_i refers to the GL quadrature nodes, and the corresponding quadrature weights are given by ω_i . Hence, we compute \mathbf{P}^e and \mathbf{Q}_x^e in (3.2) as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}^e &\approx \sum_{i=0}^p \mathcal{L}(\xi_i) \mathcal{L}^T(\xi_i) \omega_i |J| = |J| \text{diag}[\omega_0, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_p], \\ \mathbf{Q}_x^e &\approx \sum_{i=0}^p \mathcal{L}(\xi_i) (\partial_x \mathcal{L}(\xi_i))^T \omega_i |J|. \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

Once we have \mathbf{P}^e and \mathbf{Q}_x^e , we define the strong-form elemental first derivative SBP operator as:

$$\mathbf{D}_x^e = (\mathbf{P}^e)^{-1} \mathbf{Q}_x^e. \quad (3.7)$$

The weak form second-order derivative \mathbf{Q}_{xx}^e in (3.4) may now be formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Q}_{xx}^e &= \mathcal{L} (\mathbf{D}_x^e \mathcal{L})^T \Big|_0^p - (\mathbf{D}_x^e)^T \mathbf{P}^e \mathbf{D}_x^e = \text{diag} \left(-\mathbf{D}_x^e|_0, 0, \dots, 0, \mathbf{D}_x^e|_p \right) - (\mathbf{D}_x^e)^T \mathbf{P}^e \mathbf{D}_x^e \\ &= \tilde{\mathbf{B}}^e \mathbf{D}_x^e - (\mathbf{D}_x^e)^T \mathbf{P}^e \mathbf{D}_x^e. \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

The corresponding strong-form second derivative SBP operator at the element level is:

$$\mathbf{D}_{xx}^e = (\mathbf{P}^e)^{-1} \mathbf{Q}_{xx}^e. \quad (3.9)$$

3.2 Construction of the global matrices

The single element matrices computed above are next assembled to obtain the global matrices, i.e., the global mass matrix (\mathbf{P}), the global \mathbf{Q}_x matrix and the global \mathbf{Q}_{xx} matrix. This process is exemplified by considering a two-element mesh. The global

matrix \mathbf{K} is merged as:

$$\mathbf{K} = \sum_{e=1}^{N_{el}} \mathbf{K}^e = \begin{pmatrix} K_{00}^L & \cdots & K_{0p}^L & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \\ K_{p0}^L & \cdots & (K_{pp}^L + K_{00}^R) & \cdots & K_{0p}^R \\ \vdots & & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & & K_{p0}^R & \cdots & K_{pp}^R \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.10)$$

where the superscripts L and R denote the left and right element matrices, and the subscript is the associated row and column indices. The global mass matrix \mathbf{P} is thus obtained for two element as:

$$\mathbf{P} = \sum_{e=1}^{N_{el}} \mathbf{P}^e = |J| \text{diag}(\omega_0, \omega_1, \dots, \omega_p + \omega_0, \omega_1, \dots, \omega_p). \quad (3.11)$$

The global \mathbf{Q}_x matrix can now be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Q}_x &= \sum_{e=1}^{N_{el}} \mathbf{Q}_x^e = \begin{pmatrix} Q_{x00}^L & \cdots & Q_{x0p}^L & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \\ Q_{xp0}^L & \cdots & (Q_{xpp}^L + Q_{x00}^R) & \cdots & Q_{x0p}^R \\ \vdots & & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & & Q_{xp0}^R & \cdots & Q_{xpp}^R \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} Q_{x00}^L & \cdots & Q_{x0p}^L & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \\ Q_{xp0}^L & \cdots & 0 & \cdots & Q_{x0p}^R \\ \vdots & & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & & Q_{xp0}^R & \cdots & Q_{xpp}^R \end{pmatrix}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.12)$$

where at the shared node $Q_{xpp}^L = -Q_{x00}^R$. The global \mathbf{Q}_{xx} can now be computed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Q}_{xx} &= \sum_{e=1}^{N_{el}} \mathbf{Q}_{xx}^e = \text{diag} \left(-\mathbf{D}_x^L|_0, 0, \dots, 0, \mathbf{D}_x^L|_p - \mathbf{D}_x^R|_0, 0, \dots, 0, \mathbf{D}_x^R|_p \right) \\ &\quad - \left[(\mathbf{D}_x^L)^T \mathbf{P}^L \mathbf{D}_x^L + (\mathbf{D}_x^R)^T \mathbf{P}^R \mathbf{D}_x^R \right] \\ &= \text{diag} \left(-\mathbf{D}_x^L|_0, 0, \dots, 0, 0, 0, \dots, 0, \mathbf{D}_x^R|_p \right) \\ &\quad - \left[(\mathbf{D}_x^L)^T \mathbf{P}^L \mathbf{D}_x^L + (\mathbf{D}_x^R)^T \mathbf{P}^R \mathbf{D}_x^R \right], \end{aligned} \quad (3.13)$$

at the shared node $\mathbf{D}_x^L \mathbf{U}^L|_p \approx \mathbf{D}_x^R \mathbf{U}^R|_0$, which is imposed strongly by removing \mathbf{D}_x^L and \mathbf{D}_x^R . After computing the global mass matrix \mathbf{P} , the global \mathbf{Q}_x , and the global \mathbf{Q}_{xx} , the global strong form SBP operators are computed as $\mathbf{D}_x = \mathbf{P}^{-1} \mathbf{Q}_x$ and $\mathbf{D}_{xx} = \mathbf{P}^{-1} \mathbf{Q}_{xx}$, respectively.

3.3 The semi-discrete energy analysis

We may now express the semi-discrete approximation of (2.4) in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P} \partial_t \mathbf{U} + a \mathbf{Q}_x \mathbf{U} - \epsilon \mathbf{Q}_{xx} \mathbf{U} &= \mathbf{E}_0 [\sigma_0 (a \mathbf{U} - \epsilon \mathbf{D}_x \mathbf{U} - \mathbf{G})] + \mathbf{E}_N [\sigma_1 (\epsilon \mathbf{D}_x \mathbf{U} - \mathbf{G})], \\ \mathbf{U}(0) &= \mathbf{F}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.14)$$

where $\mathbf{E}_0 = \text{diag}(1, 0, \dots, 0)$ and $\mathbf{E}_N = \text{diag}(0, \dots, 0, 1)$. We now obtain the energy estimate for the semi-discrete problem by multiplying (3.14) with \mathbf{U}^T from the left and adding it to its transpose with $\sigma_0 = \sigma_N = -1$, to obtain

$$\frac{d}{dt} \|\mathbf{U}\|_{\mathbf{P}}^2 + 2\epsilon \|\mathbf{D}_x \mathbf{U}\|_{\mathbf{P}}^2 = \frac{1}{a} [\mathbf{G}_0^2 - (a \mathbf{U}_0 - \mathbf{G}_0)^2] + \frac{1}{a} [\mathbf{G}_N^2 - (a \mathbf{U}_N - \mathbf{G}_N)^2], \quad (3.15)$$

where $\|\mathbf{U}\|_{\mathbf{P}}^2 = \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{P} \mathbf{U}$ and $\|\mathbf{D}_x \mathbf{U}\|_{\mathbf{P}}^2 = (\mathbf{D}_x \mathbf{U})^T \mathbf{P} (\mathbf{D}_x \mathbf{U})$. The semi-discrete energy rate (3.15) mimics its continuous counterpart term by term. Time integration of (3.15) leads to the energy estimate:

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathbf{U}(:, T)\|_{\mathbf{P}}^2 + 2\epsilon \int_0^T \|\mathbf{D}_x \mathbf{U}\|_{\mathbf{P}}^2 dt \\ = \|\mathbf{F}_0\|_{\mathbf{P}}^2 + \frac{1}{a} \int_0^T \left[(\mathbf{G}_0^2 + \mathbf{G}_N^2) - [(a \mathbf{U}_0 - \mathbf{G}_0)^2 - (a \mathbf{U}_N - \mathbf{G}_N)^2] \right] dt, \end{aligned} \quad (3.16)$$

which again mimics the continuous estimate (2.3) term by term.

4 The fully-discrete system

We now discretize the temporal domain into M_{el} number of finite elements to obtain the fully-discrete system. In addition to the spatial discretization, the temporal discretization generates $(M+1) \times (N+1)$ global nodes, where $M = (M_{\text{el}} \times p_t)$. p_t denotes the degree of the polynomial used in temporal-direction. This is the same procedure

as in the spatial case discussed above. This results in the following vectors:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{U} &= (\mathbf{U}_0, \mathbf{U}_1, \dots, \mathbf{U}_M)^T, & \mathbf{U}_i &= (U_{i,0}, U_{i,1}, \dots, U_{i,N})^T, \\
\mathbf{F} &= (\mathbf{F}_0, \mathbf{U}_1, \dots, \mathbf{U}_M)^T, & \mathbf{F}_0 &= (f_0, f_1, f_2, \dots, f_N)^T, \\
\mathbf{G} &= (\mathbf{G}_0, \mathbf{G}_1, \dots, \mathbf{G}_M)^T, & \mathbf{G}_i &= (g_0(i\Delta t), 0, 0, \dots, g_1(i\Delta t))^T, \\
\mathbf{U}^0 &= (U_{0,0}, U_{1,0}, \dots, U_{M,0})^T, & \mathbf{G}^0 &= (g_0(0), g_0(\Delta t), \dots, g_0(M\Delta t))^T, \\
\mathbf{U}^N &= (U_{0,N}, U_{1,N}, \dots, U_{M,N})^T, & \mathbf{G}^N &= (g_N(0), g_N(\Delta t), \dots, g_N(M\Delta t))^T.
\end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

Considering the SBP operators and using the Kronecker product we now define the fully discrete system where the temporal and spatial grids are orthogonal to each other. The fully-discrete system is:

$$\begin{aligned}
\left[(\mathbf{Q}_t \otimes \mathbf{P}_x) + a(\mathbf{P}_t \otimes \mathbf{Q}_x) - \epsilon(\mathbf{P}_t \otimes \mathbf{Q}_{xx}) \right] \mathbf{U} &= \sigma_{t0} (\mathbf{E}_t \otimes \mathbf{P}_x) (\mathbf{U} - \mathbf{F}) \\
&+ \sigma_{x0} (\mathbf{P}_t \otimes \mathbf{E}_{x0}) (a\mathbf{U} - \epsilon\mathbf{D}_x\mathbf{U} - \mathbf{G}) \\
&+ \sigma_{x1} (\mathbf{P}_t \otimes \mathbf{E}_{xN}) (\epsilon\mathbf{D}_x\mathbf{U} - \mathbf{G}),
\end{aligned} \tag{4.2}$$

where the subscripts define the associated matrix computed in that corresponding direction. \mathbf{E}_{x0} and \mathbf{E}_{xN} are identical to \mathbf{E}_0 and \mathbf{E}_N in (3.14). The penalty term in the temporal direction σ_{t0} will now be evaluated by performing the fully discrete energy stability analysis.

4.1 The fully discrete energy analysis

The energy estimate for the fully discrete system can be obtained by multiplying (4.2) with \mathbf{U}^T from the left, and adding to its transpose with the choice $\sigma_{t0} = -1$, we obtain the following energy estimate:

$$\begin{aligned}
&U_M^T \mathbf{P}_x U_M + 2\epsilon (\mathbf{D}_x \mathbf{U})^T (\mathbf{P}_t \otimes \mathbf{P}_x) (\mathbf{D}_x \mathbf{U}) \\
&= \mathbf{F}_0^T \mathbf{P}_x \mathbf{F}_0 + \frac{1}{a} \left[(\mathbf{G}^0)^T \mathbf{P}_t \mathbf{G}^0 + (\mathbf{G}^1)^T \mathbf{P}_t \mathbf{G}^1 \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \left[(a\mathbf{U}^0 - \mathbf{G}^0)^T \mathbf{P}_t (a\mathbf{U}^0 - \mathbf{G}^0) + (a\mathbf{U}^N - \mathbf{G}^N)^T \mathbf{P}_t (a\mathbf{U}^N - \mathbf{G}^N) \right] \right] \\
&\quad - (\mathbf{U}_0 - \mathbf{F}_0)^T \mathbf{P}_x (\mathbf{U}_0 - \mathbf{F}_0).
\end{aligned} \tag{4.3}$$

The energy estimate for the fully discrete system (4.3) is similar to the energy estimate of the continuous system (2.3) and to the semi-discrete system (3.16) with an additional damping term $-(\mathbf{U}_0 - \mathbf{F}_0)^T \mathbf{P}_x (\mathbf{U}_0 - \mathbf{F}_0)$. The estimate (4.3) proves fully discrete energy stability.

5 The multistage-based temporal formulation

Alternatively, a one-step, multi-stage method can be employed using the multi-block technique [5] to discretize the temporal domain. In this approach, the problem is solved successively over small time intervals using fewer grid points, where the solution at the end of each interval serves as the initial condition for the subsequent one. The obvious advantage of the multistage formulation is that a smaller system of equations can be solved at each stage. We start by discretizing the temporal domain into M_{el} using the Lagrange polynomial of degree p_t , which eventually generates $(M + 1)$ nodes in the time domain, where $M = (M_{el} \times p_t)$. Then, the corresponding time and solution vectors become $\mathbf{t} = (0 = t_0, t_1, t_2, \dots, t_M = T)^T$ and $\mathbf{U} = (U_0, U_1, U_2, \dots, U_M)^T$, respectively. The original problem is now partitioned into M subproblems, and we solve the subproblems subsequently, one after another. One may write the discrete version of problem for the i^{th} stage as:

$$\begin{aligned} \left[(\mathbf{Q}_{t,i} \otimes \mathbf{P}_x) + a(\mathbf{P}_{t,i} \otimes \mathbf{Q}_x) - \epsilon(\mathbf{P}_{t,i} \otimes \mathbf{Q}_{xx}) \right] \mathbf{U}_i &= (\sigma_{t0} \mathbf{E}_{t,i} \otimes \mathbf{P}_x) (\mathbf{U}_i - \mathbf{U}_{i-1}) \\ &+ \sigma_{x0} (\mathbf{P}_{t,i} \otimes \mathbf{E}_{x0}) (a\mathbf{U} - \epsilon \mathbf{D}_x \mathbf{U} - \mathbf{G}^0) + \sigma_{x1} (\mathbf{P}_{t,i} \otimes \mathbf{E}_{xN}) (\epsilon \mathbf{D}_x \mathbf{U} - \mathbf{G}^N). \end{aligned} \quad (5.1)$$

This equation will be solved to obtain the solution vector $\mathbf{U}_i = (U_{i,0}, U_{i,1}, \dots, U_{i,m_i})^T$.

5.1 The fully discrete energy analysis for multistage based formulation

The associated energy estimate can now be obtained by multiplying (5.1) with \mathbf{U}_i^T from the left and adding to its transpose with the choices of $\sigma_{t0} = -1$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{U}_{i,m_i}^T \mathbf{P}_x \mathbf{U}_{i,m_i} + 2\epsilon (\mathbf{D}_x \mathbf{U}_i)^T (\mathbf{P}_{t,i} \otimes \mathbf{P}_x) (\mathbf{D}_x \mathbf{U}_i) \\ = \mathbf{U}_{i-1,0}^T \mathbf{P}_x \mathbf{U}_{i-1,0} + \frac{1}{a} \left[(\mathbf{G}^0)^T \mathbf{P}_t \mathbf{G}^0 + (\mathbf{G}^N)^T \mathbf{P}_{t,i} \mathbf{G}^N \right. \\ \left. - \left[(a\mathbf{U}^0 - \mathbf{G}^0)^T \mathbf{P}_{t,i} (a\mathbf{U}^0 - \mathbf{G}^0) + (a\mathbf{U}^N - \mathbf{G}^N)^T \mathbf{P}_{t,i} (a\mathbf{U}^N - \mathbf{G}^N) \right] \right] \\ - (\mathbf{U}_{i,0} - \mathbf{U}_{i-1,0})^T \mathbf{P}_x (\mathbf{U}_{i,0} - \mathbf{U}_{i-1,0}). \end{aligned} \quad (5.2)$$

The energy estimate in (5.2) is similar to that of the global system in (4.3) and proves energy stability of the fully discrete scheme for the multistage based formulation (5.1).

6 Numerical results

To analyze the performance of the new scheme, we perform mesh convergence studies using the MMS technique[19]. To evaluate the mesh convergence in time and mesh

separately, we consider the following analytical solution:

$$u(x, t) = \exp\left[\frac{x-1}{\epsilon_1}\right] \sin(x-at) \cos\left(\frac{\omega}{\epsilon_2}t\right), \quad (6.1)$$

where $\omega = 2\pi$ and ϵ_1, ϵ_2 take various values depending on the case being studied.

6.1 MMS study: temporal mesh convergence

We have solved this problem for three distinct cases where $\epsilon_1 = 1$ and ϵ_2 takes the values 1, 1/4 and 1/8. To assess the temporal order of convergence of the fully discrete formulation, sufficiently fine spatial grids are employed to ensure that the spatial discretization errors are negligible. We have considered a Lagrange polynomial of degree $p_x = 8$ within each element, supported over 100 elements, yielding $N_x = 801$ number of spatial nodes. Both the global and the multistage technique are employed to discretize the problem in the temporal direction. In the multistage technique, the number of nodes per stage is $(p_t + 1)$. Symbols N_t and p_t denote the number of nodes and degree of the polynomials used in temporal direction, respectively. The convergence studies are provided in Tables 1-3 and show super-convergence behavior for $p_t \geq 2$, with an accuracy $\mathcal{O}(p_t + 2)$. The linear basis provides an accuracy of $\mathcal{O}(p_t + 1)$.

Remark 6.1. *The global and multistage methods yield the same order of convergence, but the multistage-based formulation significantly reduces the error compared to the global method.*

Table 1: Temporal convergence studies

$a = 1, \epsilon = 0.01, \epsilon_1 = 1$ and $\epsilon_2 = 1$											
$p_t = 1$						$p_t = 2$					
N_t	CFL	Global		Multistage		N_t	CFL	Global		Multistage	
		$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$			$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$
3	997.586	5.720e+00	-	6.213e+00	-	5	498.793	1.360e+00	-	6.904e-02	-
5	498.793	1.550e+00	2.556	1.515e+00	2.763	9	249.396	7.235e-02	4.992	4.753e-03	4.552
7	332.529	7.703e-01	2.079	6.891e-01	2.341	13	166.264	1.224e-02	4.832	9.934e-04	4.257
9	249.396	4.906e-01	1.795	4.044e-01	2.120	17	124.698	3.675e-03	4.485	3.260e-04	4.154
11	199.517	3.276e-01	2.012	2.692e-01	2.027	21	99.759	1.477e-03	4.314	1.373e-04	4.093
13	166.264	2.280e-01	2.170	1.929e-01	1.998	25	83.132	7.085e-04	4.213	6.770e-05	4.053
15	142.512	1.670e-01	2.176	1.450e-01	1.993	29	71.256	3.829e-04	4.147	3.726e-05	4.024
$p_t = 3$						$p_t = 4$					
N_t	CFL	Global		Multistage		N_t	CFL	Global		Multistage	
		$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$			$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$
13	137.863	4.756e-03	-	2.710e-05	-	25	57.419	2.387e-05	6.836	3.755e-09	7.233
19	91.909	6.793e-04	5.128	3.992e-06	5.047	33	43.064	3.668e-06	6.746	5.421e-10	6.971
25	68.931	1.672e-04	5.108	9.643e-07	5.176	41	34.451	8.671e-07	6.644	1.236e-10	6.810
31	55.145	5.697e-05	5.006	3.138e-07	5.219	49	28.709	2.698e-07	6.550	3.756e-11	6.683
37	45.954	2.366e-05	4.966	1.250e-07	5.200	57	24.608	1.014e-07	6.470	1.394e-11	6.557
43	39.389	1.126e-05	4.942	5.756e-08	5.162	61	22.968	6.562e-08	6.418	9.025e-12	6.405
46	36.763	8.076e-06	4.928	4.072e-08	5.131	65	21.532	4.373e-08	6.387	6.067e-12	6.252

Table 2: Temporal convergence studies

$a = 1, \epsilon = 0.01, \epsilon_1 = 1$ and $\epsilon_2 = 1/4$											
$p_t = 1$						$p_t = 2$					
N_t	CFL	Global		Multistage		N_t	CFL	Global		Multistage	
		$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$			$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$
17	124.698	1.617e+00	-	1.590e+00	-	25	83.132	8.723e-02	-	4.951e-03	-
21	99.759	1.037e+00	2.101	1.008e+00	2.157	29	71.256	4.279e-02	4.799	2.692e-03	4.105
25	83.132	7.253e-01	2.053	6.992e-01	2.099	33	62.349	2.355e-02	4.622	1.590e-03	4.074
29	71.256	5.356e-01	2.044	5.146e-01	2.066	37	55.421	1.408e-02	4.497	1.000e-03	4.054
33	62.349	4.113e-01	2.043	3.950e-01	2.046	41	49.879	8.953e-03	4.408	6.605e-04	4.041
37	55.421	3.256e-01	2.043	3.130e-01	2.033	49	41.566	4.147e-03	4.318	3.221e-04	4.028
41	49.879	2.640e-01	2.043	2.543e-01	2.025	53	38.369	2.970e-03	4.253	2.350e-04	4.019
$p_t = 3$						$p_t = 4$					
N_t	CFL	Global		Multistage		N_t	CFL	Global		Multistage	
		$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$			$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$
25	68.931	2.987e-02	-	1.422e-04	-	137	10.133	2.704e-07	6.597	2.872e-11	6.663
31	55.145	1.171e-02	4.355	5.459e-05	4.450	153	9.066	1.313e-07	6.537	1.385e-11	6.604
37	45.954	5.148e-03	4.644	2.441e-05	4.549	169	8.203	6.893e-08	6.482	7.210e-12	6.562
43	39.389	2.498e-03	4.812	1.186e-05	4.802	185	7.489	3.853e-08	6.432	3.995e-12	6.526
49	34.466	1.321e-03	4.880	6.257e-06	4.897	201	6.890	2.268e-08	6.388	2.336e-12	6.471
55	30.636	7.500e-04	4.899	3.539e-06	4.935	217	6.380	1.395e-08	6.349	1.430e-12	6.411
61	27.573	4.515e-04	4.900	2.121e-06	4.946	233	5.940	8.899e-09	6.315	9.184e-13	6.221
67	25.066	2.852e-04	4.896	1.334e-06	4.944	249	5.557	5.862e-09	6.286	6.144e-13	6.052

Table 3: Temporal convergence studies

$a = 1, \epsilon = 0.01, \epsilon_1 = 1$ and $\epsilon_2 = 1/8$											
$p_t = 1$						$p_t = 2$					
N_t	CFL	Global		Multistage		N_t	CFL	Global		Multistage	
		$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$			$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$
37	55.421	1.254e+00	-	1.249e+00	-	33	62.349	4.380e-01	-	1.972e-02	-
43	47.504	9.161e-01	2.092	9.103e-01	2.103	49	41.566	6.658e-02	4.765	3.755e-03	4.196
49	41.566	6.992e-01	2.068	6.939e-01	2.079	65	31.175	1.906e-02	4.427	1.183e-03	4.087
55	36.948	5.515e-01	2.054	5.468e-01	2.062	81	24.940	7.445e-03	4.272	4.858e-04	4.045
61	33.253	4.463e-01	2.045	4.422e-01	2.050	97	20.783	3.498e-03	4.190	2.352e-04	4.025
73	27.711	3.096e-01	2.036	3.067e-01	2.039	113	17.814	1.858e-03	4.142	1.274e-04	4.014
79	25.579	2.638e-01	2.030	2.612e-01	2.030	129	15.587	1.078e-03	4.111	7.494e-05	4.007
85	23.752	2.274e-01	2.027	2.252e-01	2.026	145	13.855	6.684e-04	4.090	4.693e-05	4.003
$p_t = 3$						$p_t = 4$					
N_t	CFL	Global		Multistage		N_t	CFL	Global		Multistage	
		$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$			$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$
55	30.636	9.974e-03	-	4.404e-05	-	49	28.709	1.151e-02	-	1.611e-06	-
109	15.318	4.033e-04	4.690	1.870e-06	4.618	101	13.781	9.831e-05	6.586	1.029e-08	6.987
217	7.659	1.525e-05	4.756	7.120e-08	4.747	197	7.031	1.110e-06	6.711	1.023e-10	6.902
325	5.106	2.292e-06	4.692	1.056e-08	4.724	245	5.648	2.646e-07	6.575	2.359e-11	6.727
433	3.830	6.020e-07	4.660	2.751e-09	4.689	293	4.719	8.230e-08	6.528	7.353e-12	6.515
541	3.064	2.129e-07	4.668	9.789e-10	4.639	341	4.053	3.068e-08	6.505	2.802e-12	6.360
649	2.553	9.074e-08	4.686	4.213e-10	4.631	389	3.552	1.304e-08	6.497	1.219e-12	6.318
703	2.357	6.233e-08	4.697	2.907e-10	4.644	437	3.161	6.124e-09	6.494	5.984e-13	6.118
757	2.188	4.401e-08	4.703	2.060e-10	4.655	485	2.847	3.114e-09	6.489	3.161e-13	6.122

6.2 MMS study: spatial mesh convergence

We next study the order of mesh convergence in the spatial direction and again consider the analytical solution (6.1). The problem is solved for three distinct cases where

$\epsilon_2 = 1$ and ϵ_1 takes the values 1, 1/10 and 1/100. To determine the spatial order of convergence, sufficiently fine temporal grids are employed to ensure that the temporal errors are negligible. We have discretized the temporal domain using a Lagrange polynomial of degree $p_t = 10$ within each element, supported over 200 elements, yielding 2001 nodes. The multistage technique is employed, with $(p_t + 1)$ number of nodes per stage. For the spatial discretization, a series of different grids is used, where N_x and p_x define the number of nodes and degree of the Lagrange basis, respectively. The convergence studies are provided in Table 4. It shows super-convergence behavior for $p_x \geq 2$, with accuracy $\mathcal{O}(p_x + 2)$. For linear polynomials, the order of accuracy is $\mathcal{O}(p_x + 1)$.

Table 4: Spatial convergence studies

$a = 1, \epsilon = 0.01, \epsilon_1 = 1, \epsilon_2 = 1$											
$p_x = 1$			$p_x = 2$			$p_x = 3$			$p_x = 4$		
N_x	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	N_x	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	N_x	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	N_x	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$
21	2.971e-04	-	25	1.788e-05	-	49	7.781e-09	-	65	3.028e-11	-
25	1.902e-04	2.557	33	5.901e-06	3.993	61	2.849e-09	4.587	81	8.404e-12	5.825
29	1.316e-04	2.483	41	2.456e-06	4.038	73	1.228e-09	4.684	97	2.925e-12	5.854
33	9.633e-05	2.414	49	1.194e-06	4.048	85	5.956e-10	4.757	113	1.192e-12	5.881
37	7.358e-05	2.355	57	6.471e-07	4.048	97	3.155e-10	4.810	129	5.450e-13	5.908
41	5.808e-05	2.305	65	3.804e-07	4.046	109	1.792e-10	4.850	145	2.726e-13	5.924
45	4.704e-05	2.265	73	2.379e-07	4.043	121	1.077e-10	4.880	161	1.468e-13	5.915
49	3.890e-05	2.231	81	1.563e-07	4.040	133	6.772e-11	4.902	177	8.323e-14	5.989
53	3.272e-05	2.203	89	1.068e-07	4.037	145	4.427e-11	4.920	193	5.073e-14	5.720
$a = 1, \epsilon = 0.01, \epsilon_1 = 1/10, \epsilon_2 = 1$											
$p_x = 1$			$p_x = 2$			$p_x = 3$			$p_x = 4$		
N_x	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	N_x	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	N_x	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	N_x	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$
29	1.008e-03	-	33	1.839e-04	-	49	5.568e-06	-	81	4.488e-08	-
33	7.140e-04	2.673	41	7.992e-05	3.840	61	2.019e-06	4.630	97	1.569e-08	5.830
37	5.315e-04	2.580	49	3.994e-05	3.892	73	8.679e-07	4.702	113	6.407e-09	5.866
41	4.111e-04	2.502	57	2.206e-05	3.924	85	4.204e-07	4.763	129	2.936e-09	5.894
45	3.276e-04	2.437	65	1.314e-05	3.944	97	2.228e-07	4.810	145	1.470e-09	5.915
49	2.675e-04	2.383	73	8.301e-06	3.959	109	1.266e-07	4.847	161	7.901e-10	5.932
53	2.226e-04	2.338	81	5.494e-06	3.969	121	7.606e-08	4.876	177	4.499e-10	5.944
57	1.883e-04	2.300	89	3.778e-06	3.976	133	4.787e-08	4.898	193	2.687e-10	5.955
61	1.615e-04	2.268	97	2.682e-06	3.982	145	3.131e-08	4.915	209	1.671e-10	5.963
$a = 1, \epsilon = 0.01, \epsilon_1 = 1/100, \epsilon_2 = 1$											
$p_x = 1$			$p_x = 2$			$p_x = 3$			$p_x = 4$		
N_x	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	N_x	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	N_x	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$	N_x	$\ E\ _{N_t}$	$\mathcal{O}(E)$
31	2.361e-03	-	97	2.944e-05	3.188	37	3.839e-04	-	49	1.362e-04	-
37	1.563e-03	2.330	121	1.393e-05	3.384	109	1.115e-05	3.275	145	1.600e-06	4.096
43	1.112e-03	2.267	145	7.346e-06	3.537	145	3.452e-06	4.110	193	3.663e-07	5.157
49	8.320e-04	2.220	169	4.203e-06	3.646	181	1.307e-06	4.379	241	1.098e-07	5.425
55	6.464e-04	2.185	193	2.563e-06	3.723	217	5.726e-07	4.550	289	3.979e-08	5.588
61	5.169e-04	2.158	217	1.646e-06	3.780	253	2.800e-07	4.662	337	1.659e-08	5.693
67	4.230e-04	2.137	241	1.102e-06	3.821	289	1.490e-07	4.739	385	7.700e-09	5.764
73	3.527e-04	2.120	265	7.647e-07	3.852	325	8.490e-08	4.793	433	3.889e-09	5.814
79	2.987e-04	2.106	289	5.464e-07	3.877	361	5.110e-08	4.833	481	2.103e-09	5.850
85	2.562e-04	2.094	313	4.005e-07	3.896	397	3.219e-08	4.863	529	1.202e-09	5.877

6.3 A typical application

Finally, we solve a combined wave propagation and boundary layer problem considering the fully-discrete space-time SBP method. The Robin boundary condition $au(0, t) - \epsilon u_x(0, t) = g(t)$ is imposed at the inflow boundary ($x = 0$). First, we consider a steady-state problem with $g = 1$. Secondly, we solve a transient problem, where $g(t)$ takes the form:

$$g(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & t < 0.05, \\ 1 + \alpha \sin(\omega(t - 0.05)), & t \geq 0.05, \end{cases} \quad (6.2)$$

with frequency $\omega = 10\pi$ and amplitude $\alpha = 0.5$. At the outflow boundary ($x = 1$), we have imposed $u = 0$.

For the first problem, a deliberately incorrect initial solution $u(0, 0) = 0$ is considered and we study how fast we reach the correct steady solution. For the second problem, we start by imposing $u(0, 0) = 1$, and then the time varying wave is generated at $t \geq 0.5$ following (6.2). While solving this type of time-varying wave propagation problem, many schemes induce spurious oscillations unless a sufficiently fine grid is employed, especially when advection dominates diffusion as the wave propagates through the domain.

Here, we have considered an advection dominated flow with $\epsilon = 0.01$. We construct the reference solutions for each case using the explicit Runge-Kutta 4th-order (RK4) with CFL = 0.01 and a very fine spatial mesh consisting of 8th degree Lagrange polynomial supported over 300 elements. The reference solutions are mesh and time converged for all cases.

Fig. 1: Convergence of solution at time $t = 1$ sec for (left) $g = 1$ and (right) $g(t)$ takes the form of (6.2)

To analyze the efficiency of the combined space-time SBP method, we employ Lagrange polynomials of degree 4 in both spatial and temporal directions, which produce a 6th order accurate numerical scheme in either direction. We first examine the mesh convergence behavior for the steady-state problem by comparing the results with the reference solution. The results are presented in the left part of Figure 1, which

Fig. 2: Convergence of solution at $x = 0.9$ for $g = 1$ (left) and (right) $g(t)$ takes the form of (6.2)

shows the u -profile at the final time $t = 1$ as a function of x . Oscillations in the solution are observed near the boundary layer when coarse spatial meshes are used. These boundary layer oscillations vanish with the finer spatial meshes. The results show that the developed numerical scheme produces accurate results at very high CFL numbers. This highlights the efficiency of our proposed approach for steady state problems.

Next, we consider the time-dependent case. The corresponding mesh convergence studies are shown in the right part of the Figure 1. It can be seen that the numerical solutions obtained using our fully discrete SBP method monotonically converges to the reference solution with the mesh refinement.

We next examine the temporal convergence of the solution at $x = 0.9$, located within the boundary layer, for several mesh resolutions. The results are shown in Figure 2. For both the steady-state and time-dependent problems, the solutions obtained on relatively coarse meshes are in close agreement with the fine-mesh reference solutions. Moreover, as the mesh is refined, the numerical solutions exhibit a monotonic convergence toward the reference solutions.

Table 5: Detailed mesh properties for the cost-efficiency studies

Mesh properties							
SBP-SAT scheme				RK4 explicit			
Spatial		Temporal		CFL	Spatial		CFL
N_x	p_x	N_t	p_t		N_x	p_x	
601	4	201	4	4.0683	601	4	0.030
901	4	301	4	4.0683	901	4	0.023
1201	4	401	4	4.0683	1201	4	0.016
1501	4	501	4	4.0683	1501	4	0.010

To study the efficiency more quantitatively, we have conducted cost comparison studies with the traditional RK4 technique for three different frequencies $\omega = 5\pi, 10\pi$ and 20π . For each case, we have employed similar spatial meshes, described in Table 5.

The results are presented in Figure 3. The error is computed relative to the reference

Fig. 3: Cost-efficiency studies for amplitude $\alpha = 1$ with various frequencies (a) $\omega = 5\pi$, (b) $\omega = 10\pi$, and (c) $\omega = 20\pi$

solution described above. The figure illustrates the normalized error as a function of the normalized CPU time. Both the error and CPU time are normalized with respect to the RK4 results obtained using $N_x = 1501$ and a CFL number of 0.01. For the implicit space-time SBP method very coarse meshes are used in the temporal directions, whereas the RK4 method requires a very fine temporal mesh for stability. Figure 3 shows that the RK4 method carries very high computational cost compared to the SBP space-time method for all cases which highlights the computational efficiency of the implicit scheme. Roughly speaking the SBP-SAT scheme is between two to three orders of magnitude more efficient.

7 Summary and Conclusions

A high-order accurate fully discrete CG formulation in the SBP-SAT framework has been developed to solve initial-boundary value problems for advection-diffusion like equations. The energy analysis has been conducted at both the continuous, semi-discrete, and fully discrete levels, proving the stability of the method through the establishment of an energy bound.

Numerical validation by the method of manufactured solutions confirm superconvergence in both space and time with an order of accuracy $\mathcal{O}(p+2)$, for $p \geq 2$. In an application case, the fully discrete formulation efficiently captures space-time variations even on coarse meshes, demonstrating the method's computational effectiveness. The application to nonlinear problems is kept for future studies.

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Statements and Declarations

Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability

The data used in this study are described in the article. Any additional data that may be required are available upon request.

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